

**A STUDY OF CUSTOMER SATISFACTION LEVEL AND CUSTOMER PERCEPTION
OF E-PAYMENT APP SERVICES WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO TIRUNELVELI
CITY.**

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Abstract

The development of modern culture depends on payments. Systems of payment have considerably altered over time, from the stone age exchange system, during to coins and to Virtual payment. The position of demonetization turns to digital payments, which have achieved a enormous number of dealings, the bank services also gained a contemporary service through improvement of information technology. Digital payments refer to electronic consumer dealings, which include payments for merchandise and services that are entire over the internet, mobile payments at point of-sale via smart phone applications and peer-to-peer transfer between private users. In this article study an attempt has been made to the customer satisfaction level of the people who are using e-payment Apps. This paper seeks to recognize the dynamics of Tirunelveli E-Payment App by studying a variety of factors like the pricing, market share, revenue models, consumer behaviour, app convenience, etc.

INTRODUCTION

The international is shifting at a amazing velocity and technology is considered to be the key factor for these adjustments approximately us. The direction of demonetization involve both introduce new notes or coins of the same foreign money or completely replace the old currency with the new currency. On 8th November 2016, the Indian Government authorities announced the demonetization of the Rs. 500 and Rs. 1000 notes. The government's aim altered into to eliminate fake currency, fight tax avoidance, remove black cash gotten from money Laundering and terrorist finance actions and support cashless financial system.

Digital banking is defined for the reason of the automated delivery of new and customary banking services and products exclusive of setback to customers during digital interactive exchange channels. Indian government and private sector companies such as Paytm, Phonepe and Google pay had been forcefully approaching several digital payment applications, including the Aadhaar Payment app, the National Payments Corporation of India (NPCI) , the UPI app, and developed the Bharat Interface for Money (BHIM) app. Digital transfer by means of apps has brought behavioral alter and helped in the acceptance of digital payment. This has resulted in simplicity of shift of money in rural areas which was not touched prior by the digital payment method. Now a days many foreign investors want to spend in digital payment industry which is new outstanding destination because of extent of incredible growth in India.

OBJECTIVES

1. To analyse the satisfaction level of customers for convenience in payment transfer using Electronic Payment Applications
2. To find out impact of service quality on Customer satisfaction on e-payment
- 3.. To find out the overall analysis of E-payment App (Paytm/Phonepe/Google pay) services and awareness of people about E-Payment App in Tirunelveli city.
4. To study the Motivational factors which authority people to use E-Payment App services in Tirunelveli city.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

- 1.The present study is based on primary data collected from the respondents of the Tirunelveli City.
2. A well-structured questionnaire was measured to gather the information from the respondents the questionnaire was intended to study opinion and exchange or perform patterns of customer towards implementation of digital payment.

SAMPLING

Target population has been defined and collected. In this study the sampling unit was the

customers who have been using the electronic payment applications. In this study the sample survey size determined was 160 respondents.

DATA ANALYSIS

The data investigation has been discuss from responses composed from 160 various age group people who were using E- Payment App services in Tirunelveli city. Data has been obtainable in a significant way to make possible the research that is to come across the customer satisfaction level of E- Payment App. These provide the conditions to the respondents by analyzing their demographic information..

SWOT Analysis

Strength: -

- Electronic payment application is convenience since it is prepared round the clock and facilitate trouble-free payment or shift of funds anytime, anywhere.
- Electronic payment application can be used to carry out with more than 40 lacs marketers crosswise in our country
- We can give to any person through mobile number in india
- Most of what one requirements to do online can be complete through E -pay app has online retail, online reservation facilities, and online recharge.
- Various Promotional offers are more accepted among the public

Weakness:-

- In distant locations or small towns lack of good Internet bandwidth and velocity.
- Lack of IT infrastructure facility.
- Most users are unaware of e-pay can do for them and confused about how to use of e-app.
- Most Indians are used to carry out on cash and are yet to obtain used to being used to cashless business.
- Poor customer service.

Opportunities:-

- With upward technology practice people desire to create most payments from the convenience of their homes.
- The course in the number of operational professionals and busy program

Threat:-

- With lowered barriers to entrance
- surfacing concern about safety

Table -1
Demographic Profile of the Respondents

S.No	Particulars		No. of respondents	Percentage
1.	Gender	Male	92	57.5
		Female	68	42.5
		Total	160	100
2.	Age Group	20 - 30	67	41.87
		30 - 40	46	28.75
		40 -50	35	21.87
		Above 50	12	7.5
		Total	160	100
3.	Educational Qualification	School level	11	6.87
		Degree/ diploma	63	39.37
		Post Graduation	46	28.75
		Professionals	40	25
		Total	160	100
4.	Occupation	Government Employee	24	15
		Private Employee	72	45
		Professionals	28	17.5
		Business	36	22.5
		Total	160	100
5.	Monthly Income	Below 10000	17	10.62
		10000 - 20000	44	27.5
		20000 -30000	51	31.87
		30000 -40000	48	30
		Above 40,000	24	15
		Total	160	100
6.	Average	Below 5000	42	26.25

	Monthly transaction	5000 - 10000	34	21.25
		10000 -15000	55	34.37
		Above 15000	29	18.12
		Total	160	100

Table 1 Shows the demographic profile of the respondents here majority of the respondents are male (57.5 %). It is clear the out of 160 respondents 67 (41.87 %) respondents age group is 20– 30. It further shows majority 63 (39.37 %) respondents educational qualification are degree / diploma .Out of 160 respondents 72 (45 %) respondents occupation was private employee. The level of monthly income differ from one to another here 51 respondents (31.87) monthly earned the range between Rs.20000 – 300000. Average monthly transaction of the 55 respondents (34.37 %) the range between Rs. 10000 – 15000.

Table -2**Type of E- App**

S.No	Name of E- APP	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1.	Phonepe	68	42.5
2.	Paytm	57	35.62
3.	Googlepay	35	21.87
	Total	160	100

It Shows that 68 respondents (42.5 %) prefer to used Phonepe applications followed by Paytm.

Table -3**Source of Awareness**

S.No	Source of Awareness	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1.	Friends	52	32.5
2.	Tv/ News Paper	63	39.37
3.	Social Media	45	28.12
	Total	160	100

The above table shows most of the respondents (39.37 %) getting information from Tv/ Newspaper followed by Social media

Table -4**Purpose of Using E-App**

S.No	Purpose using	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1.	Money Transfer	38	23.75
2.	Payment of Bill (E.B/ Tax etc)	25	15.62
3.	Mobile Recharge	28	17.5
4.	Air/Railway Ticket	27	16.87
5.	Online Shopping	42	26.25
	Total	160	100

The above table shows most of the respondents 42 (26.25 %) prefer to using the purpose of online shopping process followed by the money transfer.

Table – 5

Level of Satisfaction

Particulars	SA	A	NI	DA	SDA	Total Weighted Score	Weighted Mean Value	Rank
	5	4	3	2	1			
Speedy delivery services	64 (320)	56 (224)	13 (39)	15 (30)	12 (12)	625	3.90	I
Save time and efforts	72 (360)	49 (196)	10 (30)	18 (36)	11 (11)	593	3.70	III
The Speed of login of your Account is fast	58 (290)	46 (184)	21 (63)	17 (34)	18 (18)	589	3.68	IV
Easier to use than Government app	48 (240)	62 (248)	14 (42)	19 (38)	17 (17)	585	3.65	V
Secured your information	44 (220)	68 (272)	18 (54)	21 (42)	9 (9)	597	3.73	II

This table reveals the satisfaction level of the respondents, speedy delivery services, secured your information got first two ranks. Easier to use than bank app considered as the least rank.

SUGGESTIONS

1. Private app companies should continue on addition good features to the e-app

2. Government payment app company provide offer enhanced services like private app companies.
3. Payment app companies provide more discount and offers to make customer.
4. Payment app companies maintain issues like privacy and misuse of the customer personal datas through payment app services.
5. Payment app companies must maintain security and safety features its help to reduce minimize the risk.
6. Payment app companies promote their services through various medias

CONCLUSION

E-app has shown a incredible increase and enlargement and its provide various services its aim at satisfying customer's needs .Respondents feel that online Payment apps provide wide variety of banking services and payments .E-app was used by most of the customers and its has offer enormous brand loyalty. Maximum respondents of Tirunelveli city are satisfied with the e-App Services ,Same time respondents are not fully fulfilled with the security and safety features of payment app and has to be complete aware. Some respondents think that there is risk using payment app services . Respondents are decided that in broad service quality of payment apps are good. Maximum respondents are fulfilled with the fast and speed dealings of the Payments Application. Respondents are decided that payments are user-friendly and easy. The respondents are also fulfilled with the comfort level and responsiveness of the App. Respondents are receiving good reduction offers and are fulfilled with the E-Payment Applications.

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